

EFFECT ON MEAN PLATELET VOLUME VALUES OF ANTIVENOM TREATMENT IN SNAKEBITES

Eylem Kantarcı^{1*}, Ali Karakuş²

Keywords

Snake bite,

MPV,

Antivenom

ABSTRACT

Mean platelet volume (MPV) is easily accessible in Hemogram (CBC), which can be routinely studied in emergency departments. In the study, it was purposed to determine the use of MPV values as follow up parameters by determining the variability with antivenom treatment in cases of snake bites. our study, 427 patients from Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Faculty of Medicine, Emergency Department were examined retrospectively after approval of the ethics committee. Patients were divided into groups which were given the snake antivenom, the untreated group, under 18 years, 18-45 years and over 45 years old. The CBC, Biochemistry, International Normalized Ratio (INR) and MPV levels of the cases were examined. It values were analyzed statistically with administration of antivenom. The data were evaluated in SPSS 23.0. In this study there were 427 patients, within that group 282 (66%) were male and 145 (34%) were female. There was a statistically important difference between MPV1 (values of arrival) ($p < 0.05$) between the ages of 18-45 which were given and nongiven antivenom. There was no significant difference between MPV 1 and MPV 2 values in other age groups ($p > 0.05$). This study is important because it is the first study to examine the MPV values in snakebite cases in the literature. In snakebite cases, MPV values may differ between ages according to antivenom treatment. It should not be used alone as a follow-up parameter in all age groups.

INTRODUCTION

Toxic snake bites are an emergency situation that requires rapid procedure. Deaths related to snake bites are common in the world. In Turkey, especially in the southern and southeastern Anatolia, it is frequently encountered¹. The most common cause of snake biting is the viperidae. Snake venom has a complex structure consisting of a combination of many toxic proteins and enzymes. The poison has cardiotoxic, hematoxic, nephrotoxic, neurotoxic and myotoxic effects. According to the severity of toxin, local and systemic symptoms are observed in the patient (Figure 1-3). Systemic complications such as fever, circulatory collapse, nausea, vomiting, jaundice, delirium, convulsions and coma may occur as well as local findings such as pain, ecchymosis, hemorrhagic edema, temperature increase, lymphangitis and tissue necrosis in the bite area^{2,7}. The most effective method is antivenom and it is critical in terms of mortality and morbidity to be administered in the well dose and as soon as possible. The known follow-up parameters after treatment are decreased hemoglobin and hematocrit values, leukocytosis, thrombocytopenia, hypofibrinogenemia, impairment in coagulation tests, proteinuria and azotemia²⁻⁷ (Table 1). In the literature, MPV values have been studied in many patient groups but no study has been found MPV values on snake bites. For this reason, we tried to determine whether the MPV values of snake bites in our study varied with antivenom treatment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In our study, 427 patients from Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Faculty of Medicine Emergency Department were examined retrospectively after approval of the ethics committee. (Date: 14.02.2017, No: 26). Hemogram (CBC), Biochemistry, INR and MPV values of the cases were evaluated. Patients with an ICD code T63.0 and X20 who were referred to emergency services were examined retrospectively from the hospital information system. The emergency service was included in the study of patients who were exposed to snakes' heat, who were enrolled in the system, CBC, Biochemistry, INR values. Patients who were enrolled in the system due to snake bite but were unable to access the laboratory study and file information were excluded from the study.

Volume: 2

Issue: 2

Page: 82-86

Received: 29.01.2024

Accepted: 22.03.2024

Available online: 30.06.2024

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12680710

1*-Hatay Training and Research Hospital, Emergency Service -Hatay, Turkey, dreylemgsms@yahoo.com, ORCID iD : 0000-0002-6117-2784

2-Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Faculty of Medicine Department of Emergency - Hatay, Turkey, drkarakus@yahoo.com, ORCID: 0000-0003-1358-3201

CBC (hemoglobin, platelet, MPV), INR and biochemical evaluations were performed in blood samples taken before the patients were given emergency medical care at the time of first admission. Blood values were statistically analyzed according to given and not given antivenom, among all ages (under 18 years, 18-45 years and over 45 years). The arrival values of the data were named 1 and the end values were 2.

MPV levels were studied throughout the groups and whether there was any difference between the groups. SPSS 23.0 program was used for the analysis of the study. $P < 0.05$ was noted statistically significant. The normal of the data was evaluated by the Kolmogorov Smirnov test for each group. Mann-Whitney U was used for non-normal dispersion, Student-t test for normal distribution.

RESULTS

In our study there were 427 patients, 282 (66%) of the patients were man and 145 (34%) were woman. 81 (19%) were under 18 years old, 214 (50.1%) were between 18-45 years old and 132 (30.9%) were over 45 years old.

There were 81 patients under the age of 18 years, within that group 61 were male and 20 were female. From this patient group, 40 were given snake antivenom. There was no significant difference in MPV 1-2 values between the groups (Table 2).

There were 214 patients that are between the ages 18-45 years old, within that group 139 (65%) were male, 75 (35%) were female. From this patient group, 70 were given antivenom. There was a statistically meaning difference at MPV1 values ($p < 0.05$) (Table 3), and there was no meaning difference at MPV2 values ($p > 0.05$) (Table 3).

There were 132 patients over the age of 45 years, within that group 82 (62.1%) were male and 50 (37.9%) were female. From this patient group, 39 were given snake antivenom. There was no meaning difference between MPV1 and MPV2 values. ($p > 0.05$).

In general, all patients were evaluated regardless of age and sex, and 149 of 427 patients were given antivenom. Despite there was a statistically meaning difference between glucose 1 and INR 1 values ($p < 0,05$) among the patients who were not given antivenom, there was not any significant difference in other parameters ($p > 0,05$).

DISCUSSION

Snake venom has wide influence on the bite area and the whole body. It consists of a combination of toxin, enzyme (such as neurotoxin, hemolysin, cardiotoxin, nucleotidase) and toxic protein. Snake bites according to the type of poison; local ef-

fects such as edema, ecchymosis can be seen. Systemic effects may include vomiting, nausea, diarrhea, hypotension, tachycardia, circulatory failure, dizziness, shock, anxiety, drowsiness, consciousness changes, acute renal failure, pulmonary edema. Thrombocytopenia, leukocytosis, anemia, increase in INR, hyperpotasemia and hypoglycemia may develop from laboratory changes [5]. Many studies have reported these side effects [8-16]. Similar findings were found in our study. Unlike the literature, MPV values were also examined. Snake bite cases should be washed with water and soap and bandaged as an emergency treatment. The extremity should be kept at heart plane and tight clothing should be removed [5]. If necessary, basic and advanced life promote should be considered. Treatment includes tetanus prophylaxis, IV hydration, antihistamines, steroids, antibiotics, and serpentine antiserum. The main treatment in snake bites is antivenom treatment. Patients should be given antiviral therapy if there is progressive signs and symptoms such as serpentine shock, rapid progressive edema, neurotoxic findings, spontaneous bleeding⁵. (Table 1) Patients were separated according to appropriate follow-up parameters and treated.

In Turkey, as a snake antivenom, the European Anti Poison Antiserum (10 ml intramuscular or intravenous ampoule) provided by and used by the Ministry of Health. There is 1 ml of horse immunoglobulin 100 mg. In our service, 1 mg/kg corticosteroid, 1 mg/kg feniramine maleate and 1 mg/kg ranitidine were given before the disease antivenom treatment. After that; for the cases that needed, an appropriate number of antivenom were practiced in 45-60 minutes with intravenous route in 100 cc SF, by slow infusion controlled. Antivenom therapy was given according to the systemic staging system. Patients with stage 0 and stage 1 poisoning findings were not treated with antivenom. Patients with stage 0 clinic were kept under observation for at least 12 hours in terms of increased tissue edema and systemic poisoning in our emergency department. Patients with stage 0 poisoning were checked for signs of snake-related tooth marks. Patients who did not have a dental sign, did not develop signs of tissue edema and systemic poisoning, were discharged after 12 hours of observation. Patients with stage 1 poisoning findings were admitted to our emergency department. The patients who were stayed stage 1 and did not show progress during their treatments, were not given antivenom. While the patients with stage 2 were observing by monitored, the patients with stage 3 were observed under intensive care. Each patients that stage 3 received antivenom therapy. In our study, there were 427 patients and 149 of these patients were given snake antivenom. There were not any complications related to antivenom developed in any of our patients.

MPV is the platelet activation parameter. It has been used since the 1980s in evaluating platelet volume. It is a value to be

Table 1. Clinical staging, antivenom use and follow-up stages in snake bite ⁷

Stage of poisoning (intoxication)	Clinic	Use of Antivenom	Follow up
No intoxication Stage 0	Dental sign can be seen, No local or systemic poisoning after bite.	Not being used	Discharged after 8 hours observation
Mild intoxication Stage 1	Mild tissue swelling , mild ecchymosis, no systemic findings. Normal laboratory findings (normal platelet count), Systolic pressure > 90 mmHg	Not being used	Can be discharged after 12 hours observation.
Modarete Intoxication Stage 2	Increased swelling, pain in that area, ecchymosis, prolonged prothrombin time, Platelet count < 80.000, Systolic pressure > 90 mmHg	Depending on the severity of the poisoning 2 vial antivenom is recommended .	Should be observed by monitoring.
Severe intoxication Stage 3	Increased swelling, pain in that area,, bullos tissue, necrosis can be observed. Prolonged prothrombin time, Platelet count < 80.000, Systolic pressure < 90 mmHg Severe systemic symptoms, coagulopathy (epistaxis, stomach bleeding etc.)	Depending on the severity of the poisoning 4 vial and over antivenom is recommended .	Should be observed in intensive care.

Table 2. Comparison of first and last values for given antivenom and not-given antivenom under 18 years

		Hb 1	Platelet 1	INR 1	Glucose 1	MPV 1
First values	Given antivenom	p>0.05	p>0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05	p>0.05
	Not given antivenom	p>0.05	p>0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05	p>0.05
		Hb 2	Platelet 2	INR 2	Glucose 2	MPV 2
Last values	Given antivenom	p<0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05	p>0.05
	Not given antivenom	p<0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05	p>0.05

Table 3: Comparison of first and last values for given antivenom and non-given antivenom between ages 18-45 years

		Hb 1	Platelet 1	INR 1	Glucose 1	MPV 1
First values	Given antivenom	p<0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05
	Not given antivenom	p<0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05
		Hb 2	Platelet 2	INR 2	Glucose 2	MPV 2
Last values	Given antivenom	p<0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05	p>0.05
	Not given antivenom	p<0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05	p<0.05	p>0.05

Figure 1.

Figure 2. ¹⁸

Figure 3. ⁷

Figure 1. Edema and ecchymosis in snakebite.

Figure 2. Necrotic lesion and diabetic foot in snakebite.

Figure 3. Patient with cardiopulmonary insufficiency followed up mechanical ventilator after on the face snakebite.

(Figures taken from Prof. D.r. Ali KARAKUŞ' s archive).

studied in a routine hemogram showing the mean volume of circulating platelets. For this reason, it is easy to reach the end result. MPV values are also increasing when platelet production increases. Vasculitis, leukemia, haemorrhages and sepsis are used as increased inflammatory markers. Platelet counts decrease with the effect of hemotoxic poisons. Because of the present hemotoxic effect of snake venom, these parameters have been a guide in patient follow-up and treatment. There are many studies in the literature that examine the MPV values except snakebite[17,18]. However, no study has been found on snake venom effect and MPV involvement. Snake venom causes spontaneous hemorrhage in advanced stages and decreases platelet counts due to toxic effect. In our study, MPV results independently of thrombocyte count did not reach significant results, except for first values MPV of 18-45 years of age.

CONCLUSION

This study is important because it is the first study to examine the MPV values in snakebite cases in the literature. In snakebite cases, MPV values may differ between ages according to antivenom treatment. It should not be used alone as a follow-up parameter in all age groups.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

Acknowledgements

No

REFERENCES

1. Karakuş A, Duru M, Kuvandık G, Kaya E, Kekeç Z. Snake Bites in Winter Season: A Case Report. *Istanbul Med J*. 2013;14(1):47-8.
2. Karakuş A. Snake bite, tibia fracture. *Turk J Emerg Med*. 2012;12(2): 101.
3. Karakuş A. Attention to compartment syndrome in snakebites! *İzmir Dr. Behçet Uz Çocuk Hast. Derg.* 2015; 5 (3):217-218.
4. Karakuş A, Kuvandık G. Hematuria after snake bite. *Firat Med J* 2016; 21(1): 229-230.
5. Karakuş A, Zeren C, Celik MM. A 5-year retrospective evaluation of snakebite cases in Hatay, Turkey. *Toxicology and Industrial Health*. 2015; 31(2): 188-92.
6. Sahan M, Duru M, Çalışkan K. Snake envenomation to the face of a child—rare case. *Prague Medical Report*. 2015;116(2): 314-320.
7. Sahan M, Taşın V, Karakuş A, Özcan O, Eryiğit U, Kuvandık G. Evaluation of patients with snakebite who presented to the emergency department: 132 cases. *Turkish Journal of Trauma & Emergency Surgery*. 2016;22(2):333-337.
8. Otkun M. Bites and insect stings. İliçin G, Ünal S, Biberroğlu K, Akalın S, Süleymanlar G (eds). *Basic Internal Diseases*. 1st Edition. Ankara: Güneş Kitabevi. 1996: 2146-2148.
9. Perez JC, Sanchez EE. Natural protease inhibitors to haemorrhagins in snake venoms and their potential use in medicine. *Toxicon*. 1999; 37: 703-28.
10. Bush SP, Siedenburg E. Neurotoxicity associated with suspected southern Pacific rattlesnake (*Crotalus viridis helleri*) envenomation. *Wilderness Environ Med*. 1999; 10 (1): 247-9.
11. Chippaux JP, Goyffon M. Venoms, antivenoms and immunotherapy. *Toxicon*. 1998; 36(2): 823-46.
12. Kurnik D, Haviv Y, Kochva E. A snake bite by the Burrowing Asp, *Atractaspis erigerddensis*. *Toxicon*. 1999; 37 (4): 223-7.
13. Boyer LV, Seifert SA, Clark RF. Recurrent and persistent coagulopathy following pit viper envenomation. *Arch Intern Med*. 1999; 159(3): 706-10.
14. Chippaux JP, Goyffon M. Venoms, antivenoms and immunotherapy. *Toxicon*. 1998; 36: 823-46.
15. Audebert F, Urtizberea M, Sabouraud A. Pharmacokinetics of Vipera aspis venom after experimental envenomation of antivenom therapy. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther*. 1994; 268(3): 1512-7.
16. Karakuş A, Ozkan M, Karcioğlu M. Diabetic Foot Due to Anaphylactic Shock: A Case Report. *Arch Trauma Res*. 2014 ; 3(1):1-3.
17. Arica S, Özer C, ARICA V, Karakuş A, Celik T, Gunesacar T. Evaluation of the Mean Platelet Volume in Children with Familial Mediterranean Fever. *Rheumatology International*. 2012;32(2):3559-63.
18. Aydoğan A, Akkucuk S, Arica S. The Analyze Of Mean Platelet Volume And Platelet Distribution With Levels İn Appendicitis. *Indian Journal of Surgery*. 2015;1(2):495-500.